

THE ROLE OF THE BENGKULU PROVINCIAL GOVERNMENT IN REGULATING LAND USE RIGHTS (HGU) TO ADDRESS SOCIAL CONFLICTS IN SOUTH BENGKULU

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ABSTRACT

The regulation of Land Use Rights (HGU) in South Bengkulu has become an increasingly pressing issue given the increasing social conflict between local communities and land concession companies. The urgency of this research lies in the need to understand how the provincial government plays a role in addressing complex agrarian issues, while also examining how HGU regulation policies affect social stability at the local level. This study aims to analyze the role of the Bengkulu Provincial Government in the HGU regulation process and identify the forms of social conflict that arise as a result of this policy. Using a qualitative approach, this study collected data through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs), and policy analysis, with the research location focusing on areas in South Bengkulu directly affected by the HGU regulation. The results show that the provincial government plays a strategic role in coordination, verification, supervision, and mediation. Despite land data remapping and synchronization, the regulation process still faces technical obstacles, a lack of company transparency, and limited resources. The findings also show that the emerging social conflicts are multidimensional, encompassing land boundary disputes, access to cultivated land, differing economic interests among residents, and unclear information regarding HGU status. Vertical conflicts between communities and companies, as well as horizontal conflicts between community groups, emphasize the need for a dialogue-based resolution approach and active community involvement. The study concludes that the effectiveness of HGU regulation depends heavily on strengthened cross-institutional coordination, increased data transparency, and more participatory policies to create agrarian justice and reduce the potential for conflict in South Bengkulu.

Keywords : HGU, Land Regulation, Provincial Government, Social Conflict.